

Circle packing in a regular hendecagon: supplemental material

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January 26, 2023

Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular hendecagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular hendecagon obtained using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that the configurations that we have reached correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, we believe that they should provide good lower bounds. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader is advised to refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular hendecagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hendecagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.487210637272	0.50158191722	41	0.13437457697	0.782161488941
3	0.449007526756	0.639008814987	42	0.132825501676	0.782871660788
4	0.400722084048	0.678617254976	43	0.131618416086	0.787009777624
5	0.358901283716	0.680453386585	44	0.130192777808	0.787961167676
6	0.328707637157	0.6849347358	45	0.128819186343	0.788954521212
7	0.321977224941	0.766702179897	46	0.127654409834	0.791968353954
8	0.29332841549	0.727238080114	47	0.126502278713	0.794644546571
9	0.268418161914	0.685085313842	48	0.125284229503	0.795998780403
10	0.256586353008	0.69557739535	49	0.124384330266	0.80095068349
11	0.247283699843	0.710660238402	50	0.122975658123	0.798889415655
12	0.241049891696	0.736670840395	51	0.121822023251	0.79965037345
13	0.230119021079	0.727322026601	52	0.120804748262	0.801769820872
14	0.225258087592	0.750528473596	53	0.119110848127	0.794432231253
15	0.218430686025	0.756130768396	54	0.118304458873	0.798498930449
16	0.213417631442	0.769943622716	55	0.117735223347	0.805478338618
17	0.205123644807	0.755716184322	56	0.116343464687	0.800848496999
18	0.199753913459	0.758824684885	57	0.115528266981	0.803766173607
19	0.198862645938	0.79384987399	58	0.114432143693	0.802421235124
20	0.189665172122	0.760122392704	59	0.113311184307	0.800342576835
21	0.185222380887	0.761175097744	60	0.112383024807	0.800628483218
22	0.179050572562	0.745165022397	61	0.111774806219	0.805185672342
23	0.176060167306	0.753231386799	62	0.110274883534	0.796568736161
24	0.172459859978	0.75416374752	63	0.109566709825	0.79905402307
25	0.169517654009	0.759011275629	64	0.108645772438	0.798149029733
26	0.166775028403	0.764035867048	65	0.107894010621	0.799440935509
27	0.16443678813	0.771329758122	66	0.107234883003	0.801852434746
28	0.161134239681	0.768089895427	67	0.106374389257	0.800990405589
29	0.158798636271	0.772627010958	68	0.10548593222	0.799422477696
30	0.156893263963	0.780204054539	69	0.104842022172	0.801305679096
31	0.153390678548	0.77061593138	70	0.104205665265	0.803080449132
32	0.151631494568	0.777333101313	71	0.103535878237	0.804115519803
33	0.149947508841	0.783918298391	72	0.102924113555	0.805833131194
34	0.14732975536	0.77971915699	73	0.10220692842	0.805678706804
35	0.145497957877	0.782816898647	74	0.101329314356	0.802749936465
36	0.144002526401	0.788716771438	75	0.100653144188	0.80277586506
37	0.142934221474	0.798642683216	76	0.100138083374	0.805175393184
38	0.139677729861	0.783278642084	77	0.0995983645584	0.806999920053
39	0.138535844662	0.790801115183	78	0.0989225450419	0.806424135283
40	0.1363143044	0.785273979182	79	0.0982894334985	0.806341676617

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hendecagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0977248129499	0.807194203945	121	0.0799837272311	0.817837460222
81	0.0972268481951	0.808976276337	122	0.079637225135	0.817467359971
82	0.096704658925	0.810190225846	123	0.0791667512875	0.814458781937
83	0.0959925120537	0.808036834228	124	0.0788693289945	0.814922538144
84	0.0954325361475	0.808259037109	125	0.07845381614	0.812861420387
85	0.0950003298988	0.810489708638	126	0.0782313636883	0.814724354126
86	0.0943743062011	0.809253054228	127	0.0779745598177	0.815807956387
87	0.0938815449145	0.810136240377	128	0.0778321251662	0.819230474747
88	0.0933152698104	0.809592463165	129	0.0775333547294	0.81930426086
89	0.0927413032418	0.808750845595	130	0.0771610484955	0.817745090027
90	0.0921768184619	0.80791242968	131	0.0769357057343	0.819229403852
91	0.0917232557597	0.80886988788	132	0.076563900283	0.817523755597
92	0.0911770966086	0.808048999322	133	0.076361130145	0.819359866511
93	0.0907553959146	0.809293797764	134	0.0761722149542	0.821440892908
94	0.0903163446358	0.810100518132	135	0.0758357598045	0.82027637843
95	0.0898869963636	0.81095301771	136	0.0755400869305	0.819921398774
96	0.0895102155987	0.812633630647	137	0.0752011210733	0.818554403507
97	0.0890712710971	0.813065224567	138	0.0752098708625	0.824721135328
98	0.0887375156862	0.815302848586	139	0.0747588266058	0.820763632234
99	0.0883535502323	0.816510091778	140	0.0744364572214	0.819554383441
100	0.087922574118	0.816731189963	141	0.074342644894	0.823329128757
101	0.0875536579784	0.817990607592	142	0.0738898101472	0.819097872398
102	0.0872002324254	0.819433677608	143	0.0736391328064	0.819278806697
103	0.0866698031356	0.817431175551	144	0.0733925080472	0.819491215369
104	0.0862415388508	0.81723072441	145	0.0732601754261	0.822209069262
105	0.085803381394	0.816726143175	146	0.072881810656	0.819350107604
106	0.0854273676823	0.81729391642	147	0.0726814296455	0.820432034542
107	0.0849927922005	0.816631868204	148	0.0725440011337	0.822892450494
108	0.084488529711	0.814512235414	149	0.072366971593	0.824414113218
109	0.0841303217472	0.815098229345	150	0.0722057130876	0.826252399742
110	0.0837119451887	0.814415263544	151	0.0719793460868	0.826553735903
111	0.0834794362504	0.817260193208	152	0.07184524586	0.828930292215
112	0.0831129660427	0.817398689681	153	0.0715609008209	0.827792296935
113	0.0827858698987	0.818218375922	154	0.0715347795498	0.832594541234
114	0.0825385702047	0.820534953993	155	0.0711857900637	0.82984440307
115	0.082161554396	0.820188142607	156	0.0707955563464	0.826066382409
116	0.08180190752	0.820093185818	157	0.0707208994065	0.829609191411
117	0.0814278350764	0.819615174777	158	0.0703496288389	0.826150290648
118	0.0810461937458	0.818890072839	159	0.0699529468206	0.822029692244
119	0.080653434263	0.817845074906	160	0.0698359541825	0.824435107779
120	0.0803003139752	0.817511903367	161	0.0695844226018	0.823622654795

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular hendecagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0692934082096	0.821820957397	182	0.0657061797765	0.830160710281
163	0.0691236182184	0.822846606136	183	0.0655494672911	0.830745074562
164	0.0689678840634	0.824168485932	184	0.0653688370772	0.830687533462
165	0.0687616660918	0.82424264121	185	0.0652428311853	0.831985348143
166	0.068556594798	0.824299272007	186	0.0649836913975	0.829850866739
167	0.0680548261368	0.817170501391	187	0.0648512505349	0.83091513329
168	0.0681489526451	0.824339300272	188	0.0646355424893	0.829810637444
169	0.0679890250994	0.825358606687	189	0.0645127724758	0.831058448773
170	0.0678440005212	0.82670425157	190	0.0644455076017	0.833714299783
171	0.0676964776947	0.827954760634	191	0.0641985298267	0.831690775567
172	0.0675084773839	0.828177494851	192	0.0640584658693	0.832401104802
173	0.0673467558927	0.829006271913	193	0.0639466717261	0.833818548546
174	0.0672170217146	0.830588916719	194	0.0637132540824	0.832031283353
175	0.0669820427183	0.829532062122	195	0.063585625073	0.832972863715
176	0.0668398033785	0.830732779172	196	0.0634802987263	0.834473110942
177	0.0667373524569	0.832893678578	197	0.063345290186	0.835166831868
178	0.0664718293875	0.830947560089	198	0.0632451425582	0.836754186734
179	0.0662556347075	0.8301890877	199	0.0630850645623	0.836728442968
180	0.0661098744877	0.831157871985	200	0.0629296062296	0.836793650682
181	0.0659118346898	0.830775591311	0	0	0

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular hendecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

Acknowledgements

The research of P.A. was supported by Sistema Nacional de Investigadores (México).

References

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